

Integrating Indigenous Game-Based Activity in Promoting Interactive Learning Development among Grade 10 Students

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ABSTRACT: Achieving quality education in the Philippines remains a knotty long-term task and continues to baffle all sectors of our society. Thus, this study determined the relationship between integration of indigenous game-based activity and interactive learning development among grade 10 students. This study employed random sampling technique in choosing the required number of respondents. They were surveyed on their profile and their level of perception in indigenous game-based activities and development in interactive learning. This study implied a questionnaire as a main tool for data collection. The gathered data obtained from their responses to the administered survey questionnaire underwent statistically treated with frequency and percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson r. The study revealed that the respondents are mostly 15 years old, 52.7% of the respondents are female, most of the respondents has 3 siblings, 40% of them are first child and 75.5% of the respondents are Roman Catholic. The study found that the relationship between game-based activities and interactive Learning among 10th-grade students varied depending on the specific learning scenario. While there was no significant relationship in group work, there was significant positive relationships in small group and think-pair-share activities. Integration of Indigenous Games is highly recommended to contribute to our understanding of how game-based activities can be used to enhance interactive Learning in educational settings, and provide important insights for educators and designers looking to incorporate games into their teaching practices.

KEYWORDS: indigenous game-based, group work, small group discussion, think-pair-share

INTRODUCTION

Indigenous games have become an alien to the generation of today, which is stated to as the millennials. Indigenous games have been played in the Philippines for many generations and typically use items or instruments indigenous to the country. Due to the lack of toys in the Philippines, kids frequently create games using only players. The Philippines has a variety of traditional games that are appropriate for children. The rich culture and/or traditions of the nation are thought to include these games. These games are beneficial to your health in addition to being enjoyable to play. This is because different games call for different skill sets. These games are very important to Filipino culture. Those traditional games are also hoped to be integrated with our Physical classes to pursue the programs and objectives of propagating contemporary spirits among the masses by promoting and institutionalizing our traditional games as a means for physical fitness and recreation and as a way to inculcate values of our rich cultural heritage. This will eventually reset to the promotion, awareness and preservation, and tradition. Interactive Learning could be construed as a capacity for interacting and learning by way of conversation, dialogue, or action. Thus, literally speaking, we could term "interactive," a method whereby the learner is viewed as a participant expected to perform certain actions. He acts as not only a listener or an observer but takes an active part in what is going on and, thus, basically, appears to actually be a driving force behind it all happening [Suvorova, 2001]. Interactive Learning is associated with many benefits for students. Group work, which is a common element of interactive Learning, more closely aligns with the collaborative methods of most occupations and professional academics.

The Department of Education is indeed very serious in its vision of "Quality Education." The implementation of the different programs in Physical Education will really train students and equip them to possess the relevant expertise, abilities, and attitudes that will make them physically, mentally, and emotionally fit towards a better individual. This study intends to know the level of Integrating of Indigenous Game-Based Activity and Interactive learning development among Grade 10 Students. The study's conclusions may have major implications not only for students but also for teachers, parents, and stakeholders as they provide empirical data on the importance of integrating indigenous game-based upon which to base their future judgments and decisions.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study's main objective was to integrate lessons and activities of Indigenous games in promoting Interactive Learning Development of the Grade 10 students that could engage students in active, fun, and meaningful Learning. The outcomes of this study's findings could be the basis for curriculum modification focusing on the integration of games as a way to develop interactive Learning among students. This study could help the teachers design instructional activities for their learners integrating group games, particularly Indigenous Games, for their social interaction and appreciation of one's culture.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the descriptive correlational method of research. This study employed a random sampling technique in choosing the required number of respondents. The target population for the study is selected Grade 10 students of Landy National High School.

The study used a students' questionnaire as the main tool for data collection. The questionnaire is divided into the following parts. The first part captured respondents' profiles. The second part gathered data about the perception of the respondents in the integration of Indigenous Game-Based Activity. It contains 5-point Likert scale questions strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which were scored as 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The third part captured the perceived level of manifestation of the respondents in the different aspects of Interactive Learning Development such as Group Work/Group Activity, Small Group discussion, and Think-pair-share [TPS]. This part will also contain 5-point Likert scale questions strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which were scored as 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

A request letter is made in conducting the study. The respondents were given questionnaires and guided in answering the questionnaires by means of discussing the instructions on how to answer the questionnaires. The respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaires. Data obtained from the accomplished questionnaires of the respondents were gathered by the researcher. The data gathered were recorded by the researcher before submission to the statistician. The data were subjected to statistical treatment.

For descriptive questions, profile, integration, and interactive learning development, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation will be applied. For correlations between the integration of indigenous game-based and perceived interactive learning development, such as group work, small group discussion and think-pair-share, pearson r was utilized at 0.5 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To give an in-depth analysis and interpretation, the gathered data are arranged thematically and sequentially resembling the presentation of the specific problems posed at the beginning of the study. The results display the ages of 110 respondents of the researcher. Most of the respondents are 15 years old which is 65.5%(72) of the total respondents while ages 16, 17, 18 and 19 is 29.1%, 0.9% and 0.9% respectively. Out of 110 respondents, 52.7% of it is female and the rest is male. This ensures that there is normality in the sampling of the participants when it comes to gender. Most of the respondents have 3 siblings while only 4.5% of the respondents have more than 5 siblings. Moreover, 19.1%, 17.3% and 14.5% of the respondents have 5, 2, 1 and 4 siblings consequently. Reflecting the emphasis of this paper, siblings can be important and unique developmental agents within these contexts when compared to coaches, parents, psychologists, and peers [Collins, 2016]; [Blazo and Smith, 2018]. The birth order of the respondents is mostly first born while there are only 2.7% are above fifth child. Out of 110 respondents, 27 are second child, 16 are third child, 12 are fourth child and 8 are fifth child. According to Coakley [2007], people utilize religion as a socially shared system of rituals and beliefs to transcend the material world and give meaning to important aspect of their lives. Religion fosters friendship; most societies see it as a means of recreation. The religion of the respondents are mostly Roman Catholic. Comprising the 75.5% of 110 respondents. The rest are Iglesia Ni Cristo (12.7%), Saksi ni Jehovah (1.8%), Born Again (7.3%), Seventh Day Adventist (1.8%) and .9% of the respondents prefer not to say.

Indigenous games as one of the play activities can be used as a learning resource to meet the needs of children in developing the potential include cognitive, language, emotional, social and physical motor. The result shows the perception of Grade 10 students in Integrating Indigenous Game-Based Activities. The respondents observed that they can play the games correctly with mastery; they expressed a lot of freedom in the Game; they feel competent at the Game; engaging them in the games increases their enthusiasm towards Learning; the ability to play the Game matches the game challenges; and they foster positive attitude toward the activity. Considering the majority of the item statements, the respondents really observed the Integration of Indigenous Game-based Activity.

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Table 1. Relationship between the Integration of Indigenous Game-based Activity in Promoting Interactive Learning Development among Grade 10 Students

Game-based activity	Interactive Learning Development		
	Group Work	Small Group Discussion	Think, Pair, Share
Integration	.162	.367**	.247**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results describe the results of the study that tested the correlation between game-based activities and interactive learning development among 10th-grade students. According to the Table shown, the study found that there was no significant relationship between game-based activities and interactive learning development in terms of group work ($r=0.162$). This means that there was no clear connection between playing games and improving interactive learning skills when students worked in larger groups. However, the study find significant positive relationships between game-based activities and interactive learning development in two scenarios: small group discussion ($r=0.367$) and Think-Pair-Share ($r=0.247$). One possible explanation for this is that in larger group settings, individual contributions maybe diluted, making it difficult for students to engage in meaningful interaction with each other. In contrast, the positive relationships found in small group and think-pair-share activities suggest that game-based activities may be more effective for promoting interactive Learning when students are given more opportunities to engage with each other in focused, collaborative learning environments.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study aims to integrate indigenous Game-based Activities in developing Interactive Learning among Grade 10 Students. Specifically, it determined the respondents' level of perception in integrating indigenous game-based activities and level of manifestation in interactive Learning. These findings suggest that the Integration of Indigenous Game-Based Activity can be an effective strategy for promoting interactive learning development among high school students. The demographic characteristics of the respondents may also provide useful insights for educators and researchers interested in tailoring interventions to specific populations. Integration of Indigenous Games is highly recommended to contribute to our understanding of how game-based activities can be used to enhance interactive Learning in educational settings, and provide important insights for educators and designers looking to incorporate games into their teaching practices. Future Researchers in this area could further explore the conditions under which game-based activities are more effective for promoting interactive learning development and identify specific design elements that are most likely to facilitate Learning in different contexts.

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Integrating Indigenous Game-Based Activity in Promoting Interactive Learning Development among Grade 10 Students

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